

**Management Training For Increasing Teacher Professionalism At Public Junior High School 4,
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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to examine the research program to increase teacher professionalism at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri, the factors that support the implementation of training to increase teacher professionalism at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri and the factors that hinder the evaluation procedure of teacher professionalism improvement training at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri. . The research was conducted using qualitative methods, data collection was carried out by means of observation, interviews, and document review. This qualitative method is used for several reasons. The place of research is SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri and the informants are teachers who teach at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri. The results of the study show that in the certification program, where the certification program in the implementation of teacher professional development in this school has been carried out to the maximum, for that the professionalism of educators must be improved and developed. Educators and education staff are professionals who demand the existence of an adequate skill or skill for a teacher in carrying out their profession. From the results of the study, it can be concluded that the supporting factors that increase the professionalism of teachers carried out by SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri are quite good, including training activities, attending education and training (training) attending workshops and following those related to the curriculum, for example curriculum technical guidance for development themselves and improve the professional competence of teachers.

Keywords: Management, Training, Teacher Professionalism

INTRODUCTION

Quality education is one of the foremost elements in human resource development, which in turn makes a very significant contribution to national development. In line with this, according to Sowiyah (2005) that the quality of education is one of the pillars of human resource development which is very meaningful for national development. Thus it can be said that the future of a nation lies in the quality of the education it provides (Mantja, 1998). Therefore, every educational institution, including junior high schools, needs to formulate breakthrough programs, as an effort to meet the demands of the field regarding the quality of human resources.

The low quality of education, both types, levels and units of education is currently being highlighted by various groups. Therefore, development priorities are directed at improving the quality of human resources (HR), because the quality of human resources is a parameter of the progress of a nation's development. This is in line with the opinion that "Increasing human resources is a parameter of the nation's progress because the education sector is seen as the main key to the quality of the nation" (Konapsi in Sowiyah, 2005:1).

Teachers as one of the elements that have a key role in developing the quality of human resources, need to be professionally prepared to be able to provide quality education. One of the professional development efforts of teachers is through teacher professional improvement training. In Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the professional workforce system in charge of planning and implementing the learning process, through learning outcomes, conducting guidance and training, as well as conducting research and community service.

Soewondo (in Sowiyah, 2005) asserts that the Law clearly mandates that teachers must be able to appear professionally, both inside and outside the classroom. Thus, the demand that education personnel are obliged to create a learning system that is meaningful, fun, creative, dynamic, and dialogical (Depdiknas

2003) can be realized when professional teachers are teachers who promise to provide quality services to students. He is proficient in teaching, has a commitment to his teaching task, is trustworthy, and is able to work together with others in strong coordination. Hardjana (2002).

Law Number 19 concerning National Education Standards, including educational standards, in this case teachers, are required, namely: (1) academic quality for teachers is D-IV/S1, and (2) competencies that include pedagogics, personality, professional and social for teachers. Meanwhile, those who are civil servants but do not meet the required standards must go through certification and are currently being implemented by universities appointed by the government. Through this implementation, future teachers with outstanding achievements will emerge who are believed to be able to follow the rhythm of developments in the era of very tight and fast competition now and in the future. In other words, "professional teacher profiles are truly believed to be able to adapt to developing situations and conditions" (Senduk, 2007:17).

Various government efforts have been made to improve the quality of human resources, and one of them is through training for teachers. Training is an element that is no less important in efforts to improve the quality of education and teaching in schools. Therefore, research must be carefully structured based on scientific methods and guided by what is needed now and in the future, and good training accompanied by good planning and implementation (Sewiyah, 2005).

Through training for teachers that is carried out in a planned, directed and sustainable manner, it is hoped that teachers who are successful in carrying out their professional duties can be obtained. "Practice is basically seen as an application to improving skills and is therefore necessary to learn how to carry out specific tasks" (Moekijat (1991: 101). Training is already a fairly important management responsibility, as this function has gained recognition due to the acceptance it has received. more about training as an investment in human investment.

Based on the results of initial observations, it was shown that the professional improvement training for teachers at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri experienced various obstacles so that they tended to make less significant contributions to improving the quality of education in schools. The obstacles faced, namely: (1) limited funds for research programs, (2) inadequate readiness of public facilities, (3) unavailability of standard research formats, (4) training management has not run effectively and efficiently, and (5) limited human resources that have been specially prepared. The information obtained revealed that improving the quality of human resources, in this case teachers, has been carried out through teacher professionalism training in various fields of study. However, The efforts that have been made have not yet reached the expected target. In order for the expected target to be achieved, it is necessary to manage teacher professional improvement training which is carried out in a planned, regular and continuous manner in accordance with growing demands and needs.

Based on the background described above, it makes researchers interested in researching the management of teacher professional improvement research. The research background is SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri. The choice of SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri is located in Mokupa Village, Tombariri District, far from the district capital as the center of government and trade, and is in the midst of a community whose livelihoods are relatively agriculture and fishing.

The purpose of this research is to examine:

1. Research program to increase teacher professionalism at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri.
2. Factors that support the implementation of teacher professionalism training at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri.
3. Factors that hinder the evaluation procedure of teacher professionalism improvement training at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri.

In particular, this research is useful for the heads of District and City Education Offices, school principals, and teachers to be used as feedback materials in the context of developing research programs to improve teacher professionalism in the future.

METHODS

This type of research uses a qualitative descriptive approach. Qualitative research is research that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects such as behavior, description in the form of words and language, in a special natural context and by utilizing various natural methods (Maleong, 2007:6). Qualitative research does not use the term population, but uses a "social situation" or social situation which consists of three elements, namely: place, actors, and activities that interact synergistically.(Sugiyono, 2005:207). This qualitative approach was taken because in this research the target or object of the research is limited so that the data taken can be extracted as much as possible and so that in

his study it is not possible to widen the object. This research starts from the way of inductive thinking, then thinking deductively, this research considers the data is the inspiration of the theory.

The activities of data collection and data analysis will take place simultaneously or simultaneously. According to Irfan et al, (2001) the process of qualitative research feels that it is not based on what it does not know, thus giving rise to new questions and meanings as a result of interpretation based on the perspective of the emic category (the meaning given by behavior) and the category of ethical perspective (the meaning of the researcher's interpretation). According to Bogdan and Beklen (1982), Miles and Huberman (1998), data analysis in qualitative research is carried out from the beginning when the data collection process is in the field, and after the data is collected completely even throughout the research process.

DISCUSSION

Research program to increase teacher professionalism at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri.

In improving teacher professionalism, it can be done through a certification program, where the certification program is a program from the government which aims to provide recognition from the government to the teaching profession as professional educators. The implementation of the school certification program provides services for teachers to be able to participate in the certification program.

According to the results of observations made by the author using the documentation method, data on the state of teacher certification in SMP Negeri 4. Then from the observations made by the author based on the statement of the Deputy Head of Curriculum during the interview that most of the PNS teachers have been certified, while those who are still honorary are there. Some are certified and some are not. In this program, we followed the government's program several years ago when a certification program was rolled out starting from the portfolio, then some starting from the PLPG, all of which were followed according to the applicable rules or those outlined by the government.

Then it can be seen that all the teachers of SMP NEGERI 4 Tombariri have S1 qualifications and some even have S2. This condition clearly meets the minimum requirements for a teacher, namely Strata 1. However, based on the data above, there are still some teachers who do not match the academic qualifications they have with the subjects being taught. This condition must be a concern, especially for school principals to motivate teachers as educators to improve their competencies. However, the teaching abilities of teachers who have met the qualifications are still limited, so they need guidance and training to deepen their insight and skills so that their competencies can continue to increase. From the observations made by the author,

The results of the study show that the certification program is the same as the qualification program, namely from the government, where in the certification program there are several teachers who have not been certified, the principal in the implementation of teacher professional development in this school has been carried out to the maximum, but these programs there is still a more optimal implementation process because some teachers are already running these programs. School efforts for this program are always carried out.

Furthermore, in integrated competency-based training programs, schools often involve teachers in training and education activities both inside and outside the school. Various forms of training exist such as seminars, training, workshops or workshops and many other training activities.

The certification program is a program from the government intended for teachers as a form of recognition as professional teachers. The school has never prevented teachers from participating in the certification program. In following certification, there are many conditions that must be met, and in this case the school has helped complete the requirements that must be met in certification, such as involving teachers in scientific activities which are a requirement for participating in certification, then they have arrived at the whitelist (list wait) when it's time for the school to allow it.

Teachers are an important element in the success of education. Therefore, to become a teacher, one must meet the qualifications that must be possessed by a teacher. Article 10 of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, which is regulated later in the Regulation of the Minister of National Education Number 16 of 2007 concerning Academic Qualification Standards and Teacher Competencies, states that there are four competencies that must be possessed by teachers.

4 teacher competencies according to the above Act are: 1. Pedagogic competence is the ability or skill of a teacher to manage the learning process or teaching and learning interactions with students.

2. Personality competence is related to the personal character of the teacher that reflects a positive personality, namely: sociable, patient, disciplined, honest, humble, authoritative, polite, empathetic, sincere, noble, acts according to social & legal norms, and so on.

3. Teacher professional competence is the extent to which a teacher masters the subject matter being taught, along with its structure, concepts, and scientific mindset.

4. Social competence is related to communication skills, attitudes and interactions in general, be it with students, fellow teachers, education staff, parents of students, to the wider community.

What is needed for teacher professional development is a teacher professional development program. For that, smart teachers must know how to improve teacher professionalism. How to improve teacher professionalism can be done in various ways. Efforts to improve teacher professionalism must be supported by many parties such as the government, institutions where smart teachers teach, and smart teachers themselves. The following are six ways to increase teacher professionalism:

From the results of observations and interviews, there are several things that can be done to improve teacher professionalism:

1. Continuing education to a higher level

One of the government's efforts to improve the professionalism of teachers is to provide qualifications and requirements for higher levels of education for teaching staff from school to university levels. The government also organizes programs so that teachers have adequate accountability to carry out wars and their function in educating students.

2. Actively participate in KKG (Teacher Working Group) and Teacher Community activities

The strategy of teacher professional development can be carried out by participating in activities aimed at upgrading the abilities and skills of teachers. To get inspired, you don't have to learn from a professor or someone who has a higher degree than us. In fact, learning from fellow teachers who have succeeded in practicing strategies or major breakthroughs is very important learning because it is not just a theory.

3. Participate in training that supports the quality of learning

Coaching and professional development of teachers can be done by participating in trainings. Currently, there are a lot of trainings aimed at improving the professionalism of teachers both online and offline. Smart teachers can take part in various trainings that teach various skills to support learning such as IT training, drawing, coding, and so on. So to become a professional teacher Smart teachers do not only learn about learning strategies but must be balanced with other skills as well.

4. Read a lot

Books are a source of learning not only for students, but also for teachers. Don't let smart teachers just tell students to like reading without setting an example for them. Smart teachers can read books that contain knowledge about lesson content, pedagogic competence, ways of communicating, and so on. Reading sources can come from school libraries, personal collections, articles, and also digital books that can be accessed via the internet.

5. Peer Observation and Evaluation

The form of activities that can improve teacher competence is through peer observation and evaluation activities. Smart teachers don't need to be ashamed to ask for input from colleagues on how to teach, the media that smart teachers make, and also the assessments that smart teachers carry out. If there are colleagues who are considered to have more skills or knowledge, do not hesitate to ask permission to make observations or ask questions.

6. Creating Writings

What teachers need to develop in addition to attending seminars, reading books, and asking others is to write papers. As a teacher, smart teachers are highly encouraged to write a lot, especially on the theme of education and teaching. The results of smart teachers' writings in the form of research, articles, journals, or good teaching practices can be used as documentation of what smart teachers have done and also one method to improve the ability of smart teachers to express concepts and ideas. Without a smart teacher realizing the written work that a smart teacher produces can be used as a portfolio or even a source of inspiration for other teachers.

Factors that support the implementation of teacher professionalism improvement training at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri.

There are several factors that support the professionalism of a teacher including the qualifications of teacher standards and the relevance of the teacher's field of expertise to teaching tasks, abilities and motivation, teacher education level, work experience, mastery of social competence, pedagogic and skills.

Uzer (2002:V) suggests that the teacher as a teacher or educator is one of the determining factors for the success of any educational effort. That is why every educational innovation, especially in the curriculum and improvement of human resources, the main factor always boils down to the teacher. The teacher is an influential component in improving the quality of education in schools, so that the professional ability or competence of a teacher greatly determines the quality of education.

As seen, the results of interviews and observations can be evidence that schools provide wider opportunities for all educators to participate in various training activities, workshops, training and other activities. This is carried out by sending school representatives according to the number of requests (invitations) from the implementing committee, and the implementation is carried out in turns, with the aim that all educators are able to gain insight, knowledge, and experience to further improve their competence and quality of learning. However, in determining the representatives of the activity participants, the school also adjusts the focus/material of the activities held so that each activity that is attended by educators is appropriate and able to achieve satisfactory results. The results of observations and interviews show that one of the supporting factors, namely the subject teacher deliberations (MGMP) is a non-structural organization that is independent, based on kinship, and does not have a hierarchical relationship with other institutions. Where MGMP is a forum or professional forum for teachers (classes/subjects) located in a school district/city/sub-district area whose working principle is a reflection of the activities of, by, and for teachers from all schools. Where in this forum all teachers can hold discussions and exchange ideas about the problems faced by their respective schools. In addition, this forum is a professional forum for teachers to improve their knowledge, abilities and skills. Where MGMP is a forum or professional forum for teachers (classes/subjects) located in a school district/city/sub-district area whose working principle is a reflection of the activities of, by, and for teachers from all schools. Where in this forum all teachers can hold discussions and exchange ideas about the problems faced by their respective schools. In addition, this forum is a professional forum for teachers to improve their knowledge, abilities and skills. Where MGMP is a forum or professional forum for teachers (classes/subjects) located in a school district/city/sub-district area whose working principle is a reflection of the activities of, by, and for teachers from all schools. Where in this forum all teachers can hold discussions and exchange ideas about the problems faced by their respective schools. In addition, this forum is a professional forum for teachers to improve their knowledge, abilities and skills.

Increasing teacher professionalism is ultimately up to and determined by the teachers. What efforts should be made by teachers to improve their professionalism? According to Purwanto (2002), teachers should always try to do the following:

- a. Understand the demands of existing professional standards,
- b. Achieve the required qualifications and competencies,
- c. Building good and broad peer relations, including through professional organizations,
- d. Develop a work ethic or work culture that prioritizes high quality service to constituents,
- e. Adopting innovation or developing creativity in the use of the latest information and communication technology so as not to be left behind in their ability to manage learning.

Efforts to understand the demands of existing professional standards must be placed as a top priority if our teachers want to improve their professionalism. This is based on several reasons.\

First, global competition now allows for cross-border mobility of teachers. Second, as a professional, a teacher must follow the demands of professional development globally, and the demands of the community who want better services. The only way to meet the standards of this profession is to learn continuously throughout life, by being open to hearing and seeing new developments in the field. Then efforts to achieve the required qualifications and competencies are equally important for teachers. With the fulfillment of adequate qualifications and competencies, the teacher has a strong bargaining position and fulfills the required requirements. This competency can be achieved through in-service training and various other efforts to obtain certification.

Furthermore, efforts to build a work ethic or work culture that prioritizes high-quality service to students is a must in today's era. All fields are required to provide excellent service. Teachers must also provide excellent service to their constituents, namely students, parents and schools as stakeholders. Moreover, education services are public services that are funded, provided, controlled by and for the public interest. Therefore, teachers must be accountable for the implementation of their duties to the public.

One more thing that can be pursued to increase teacher professionalism is through the adoption of innovation or creativity development in the use of educational technology that utilizes the latest information and communication technology. Teachers can take advantage of new media and ideas in the field of educational technology such as presentation media, computers (hard technologies) and also new approaches in the field of educational technology (soft technologies). The efforts of teachers to improve their professionalism ultimately require the support of all relevant parties so that they can actually be realized. The parties that must provide their support are professional organizations such as PGRI, the government and the community.

Factors that hinder the evaluation procedure of teacher professionalism improvement training at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri.

It is a challenge to minimize the inhibiting factors for increasing teacher professionalism, including factors of facilities and infrastructure, the quality of teacher education, the level of welfare and so on. Problems about teacher training to make teachers a professional. Factors constraining the development of teacher competence include the problems of teachers in improving competence including, the preparation of lesson plans that are not in accordance with the specified time, the application of strategies, methods and learning techniques that are less varied, teachers rarely use media/props that are in accordance with the characteristics of students. There are still many teachers who do not fully pursue their profession. This is due to the fact that many teachers work outside of their working hours to meet the needs of daily life so that there is no time to read and write to improve themselves. Lack of teacher motivation in improving self-quality because teachers are not required to research as is applied to lecturers in universities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted at SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri, it can be concluded:

1. The results of the study show that in the certification program, where the certification program in the implementation of teacher professional development in this school has been carried out to the maximum, for that the professionalism of educators must be improved and developed. Educators and education staff are professionals who demand the existence of an adequate skill or skill for a teacher in carrying out their profession.
2. From the results of the study, it can be concluded that the supporting factors that increase teacher professionalism carried out by SMP Negeri 4 Tombariri are quite good, including training activities, attending education and training (education and training) attending workshops and following those related to the curriculum, for example curriculum technical guidance. for self-development and improving the professional competence of teachers. The efforts of teachers to improve their professionalism ultimately require the support of all relevant parties so that they can actually be realized.
3. Factors constraining the development of teacher competence include the problems of teachers in improving competence including, the preparation of lesson plans that are not in accordance with the specified time, the application of strategies, methods and learning techniques that are less varied, teachers rarely use media / teaching aids in accordance with student characteristics. There are still many teachers who do not fully pursue their profession.

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